

FIFTEEN YEARS OF PRIMARY SOURCES ON COPYRIGHT (1450-1900)

CHANGING WORLD VIEWS
AND WHAT COMES NEXT

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Fifteen Years of Primary Sources on Copyright (1450-1900): Changing World Views and What Comes Next

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Edited by Lionel Bently, Martin Kretschmer and Elena Cooper

Abstract

This working paper presents an edited transcript of a public lecture delivered at CREATE, University of Glasgow, on 16 October 2023, celebrating fifteen years of the digital archive *Primary Sources on Copyright (1450-1900)* edited by Lionel Bently and Martin Kretschmer.** The archive charts the history of copyright from the advent of the printing press to 1900, through the selection, digitisation and analysis of primary source material by an ever-growing team of 'national editors'. When launched in 2008, the archive contained five sections (UK/Britain, France, Italy, German speaking countries, US). It has since expanded, through the addition of new sections (Spain, the Netherlands, Scandinavia, the Vatican, Jewish legal sources, Portugal and Brazil) and as well as further material for two original sections (UK and France). As *Primary Sources on Copyright* continues to expand - new Scottish material for the UK section is anticipated in 2024-25 - a panel of eleven national editors met in Glasgow in October 2023, publicly to debate questions posed by Bently and Kretschmer, about the archive's future.

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** www.copyrighthistory.org

Editorial Introduction by Lionel Bently, Martin Kretschmer and Elena Cooper

In March 2008, a conference was held at Stationers' Hall, London, to launch the Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC) funded digital archive *Primary Sources on Copyright (1450-1900)*. Edited by Lionel Bently and Martin Kretschmer, the archive in 2008 contained 5 national sections with initially 50 key source documents and original commentaries, each overseen by a specialist national editor: Ronan Deazley for Britain/UK, Friedemann Kawohl for German speaking countries/German Empire, Frédéric Rideau for France, Joanna Kostyło for Italy and Oren Bracha the United States. Since that time, *Primary Sources on Copyright* has grown in its reach, such that it now also includes sections for Spain (José Bellido), the Netherlands (Stef van Gompel and Marius Buning), Jewish law sources (Neil Netanel), Portugal and Brazil (Patricia Akester and Victor Drummond), the Vatican (Jane Ginsburg) and Scandinavia (Marius Bruning). Supplementary material has also been added to the French and UK sections about copyright and the visual arts by Katie Scott and Elena Cooper. The addition of further documents to the UK section, looking specifically at Scottish perspectives on copyright history and edited by Amy Thomas, is anticipated for 2024-5.

Primary Sources on Copyright is currently hosted by CREATE, and in October 2023, a conference was held in Glasgow, to celebrate fifteen years of the archive. The conference was endorsed by the International Society for the History and Theory of Intellectual Property ('ISHTIP') which shares a common root: the Stationers' Hall 2008 conference was also the occasion for ISHTIP's foundation. The Glasgow conference in October 2023, comprised two days of research presentations by national editors, discussion as to the future of the archive, as well as an evening public lecture – *Fifteen Years of Primary Sources on Copyright (1450-1900): Changing World Views and What Comes Next* – in which Bently and Kretschmer convened a conversation with a panel of national editors from all over the globe: Patricia Akester, José Bellido, Marius Buning, Elena Cooper, Victor Drummond, Joanna Kostyło, Magne Klasson, Jane Ginsburg, Friedemann Kawohl, Frédéric Rideau, Katie Scott and Stef van Gompel.

This Working Paper comprises a record of that public lecture, which was the occasion for debate about not just 'what comes next' for the archive, but also to reflect on the future trajectory of copyright history as a discipline. In the past three decades, copyright history has become a burgeoning intellectual field, and *Primary Sources* has created a focus for an international and interdisciplinary scholarly community. At the time of writing, there is scholarly impetus to take further what has been learnt from unearthing and extensively documenting primary sources. After almost 30 years of sustained scholarly investment, of which *Primary Sources on Copyright* has played a central role, are we on the brink of a New History of Copyright? For instance, do

copyright's origins in privileges still matter? As copyright history scholarship has become more empirical, what can we learn about the law in action, from documents about contracts and practices? What perspectives are offered by histories of copyright focussing on media other than books (e.g. visual art and drama)? What patterns can we identify about transnational flows in ideas *between* national jurisdictions, as opposed to structuring knowledge around perceived 'national traditions'? How was copyright adapted, refracted and resisted through processes of colonisation, and how do those perspectives differ depending on the status of the colony in question? What new and critical perspectives can we glean about the influence of the romantic author on the history of copyright, and are there implications for the arrival of AI technologies today? These are some of the bigger questions to which we should now turn.

Transcript of public lecture

Fifteen Years of Primary Sources on Copyright (1450-1900): Changing World Views and What Comes Next, held on Tuesday 17th October 2023, 5.30pm-7pm, Advanced Research Centre, University of Glasgow.

Claire McDiarmid, School of Law, University of Glasgow

Well, good evening everybody. My name is Professor Claire McDiarmid and I am the Head of the School of Law here at the University of Glasgow. This is my eleventh day in post, so I'm particularly pleased to be here with you, and I'm really delighted to have this opportunity to welcome you all to this public lecture as part of the Conference celebrating 15 years of the digital archive *Primary Sources on Copyright, 1450 to 1900*,¹ also referred to as *PSOC*.

Tonight's event is concerned with changing world views and what comes next in relation to the *PSOC* archive. The conference is hosted by the CREATE centre, and many of you will know all about CREATE, but because this is a public lecture, I wanted to say a little more about it. CREATE was established in 2012 as the *UK Centre for Copyright and New Business Models in the Creative Economy*. At the time it was very unusually funded by three research councils: the AHRC, the EPSRC and the ESRC. Currently it is funded by the Arts and Humanities Research Council, as UK Research infrastructure, and it has a focus on the regulation of creativity, technology and markets. As it has evolved, CREATE has adjusted its footprint to include wider questions of digital regulation and a more sustained interdisciplinary approach. It also now includes a significant competition law and tech-AI dimension. It has recruited a new Chair in Social Data Science: that's Kris Erickson. And he, along with Magali Eben, are formally appointed as deputy directors of CREATE.

CREATE is proud to host *Primary Sources on Copyright*, and with the University of Cambridge to be its general editor. The archive covers the period from the invention of the printing press, in around 1450 to the Berne Convention on Copyright in 1886, when the outlines of the modern copyright regime were settled. It is worth noting that CREATE also hosts the copyright evidence portal,² which gives access to the world's current knowledge about copyright law and its effects, and the copyright user online resource³ which is aimed at making UK copyright law accessible to creators, media professionals, entrepreneurs, students, and members of the public.

¹ www.copyrighthistory.org

² www.copyrightevidence.org

³ www.copyrightuser.org

The *Primary Sources on Copyright* archive has become a global reference point. This is one of the reasons that the Arts and Humanities Research Council invited CREATE's application to become UK Research infrastructure. Tonight's event is an opportunity to introduce, to those of you who don't know it, this historical archive, and to reflect on what has already been learnt through it and about it, and perhaps to look to its future. Martin Kretschmer, Professor of Intellectual Property Law here in the School of Law, and the Director of CREATE, and Lionel Bently, Herchel Smith Professor of Intellectual Property Law at the University of Cambridge, who are *PSOC's* co-editors, are going to lead a discussion with a panel of almost all of its national editors. On behalf of the School of Law, I warmly welcome all of you to the University of Glasgow this evening, and I'm certain that your discussion to come will be both fascinating and worthwhile. Thank you.

Martin Kretschmer

Thank you very much for these kind words Claire. This event is a hybrid event which includes most national editors of the *Primary Sources on Copyright* project: there is a whole row here in front of you, and some of the national editors are on screen, in cyberspace. In particular, I would like to introduce Lionel Bently. We jointly wrote the initial application for *Primary Sources* in 2004, and Lionel in many ways is the *spiritus rector* behind this project. Excellent that you can be with us.

During the next ten minutes, I'll attempt a live demonstration of what this project is all about.

Primary Sources was conceived in 2004. It was launched at Stationers' Hall in 2008. I thought it might be a nice start to scroll down to the programme at Stationers' Hall,⁴ where you will see some of our younger selves with the Stationers' Charter of 1684, and some of the national editors who we have here today: Frédéric Rideau, Friedemann Kawohl and Joanna Kostyło. Some of us have aged by fifteen years, but not all!

The Digital Archive is an edited collection. There is an editorial board that produced guidance to the national editors how to select. We have not attempted a comprehensive or mass digitisation project; we conceived a selective view of history, produced with the aim to challenge the prevailing narrative. We will come to that in the discussion.

I will show you now some of the documents. We have assembled, as you can see, 720 primary sources, used by about 300,000 unique visitors. The archive relies on about 50 GB of file storage. This is quite demanding use that requires support at the 'back end'. The database is built on an

⁴ <https://www.copyrighthistory.org/cam/index.php?select=news>

open source system which has stood the test of time, but it requires continuous work. In part, the purpose of today's conference is to take stock where we are and what we need to adjust for the future.

The open access book *Privilege and Property: Essays on the History of Copyright* (ed. Deazley, Kretschmer and Bently, 2010, OpenBook)⁵ is the companion volume to the archive. It is also available for free download, which was in the humanities at the time still quite unusual. The book has had 12,000 downloads, and 50,000 reads on Google books. So the material *is* being used. And what is particularly interesting to us, as editors is how it's being used and *why* it's being used.

We find that the dominant national narrative still prevails. Colleagues and scholars, lawyers across the globe, look for their *own* sources; they are not necessarily interested in what came from a Venetian privilege that moved into a different context, and then formed a precedent for something which became the Statute of Monopolies in another jurisdiction. The dominant interest is still the national justification of the system each country arrived at. Unsurprisingly the most used document in the resource is the Statute of Anne, which any English speaking copyright lawyer will know almost by heart.

If you click on United Kingdom, you get all the documents in chronological order. Here is the Statute of Anne of 1710 (the national editor for the UK was Ronan Deazley).⁶ You then have a full catalogue entry according to bibliographical standards. You get facsimile images. This one is from the Parliamentary Archives; written on parchment and stored as a roll. You can increase the size, and what you find here – which wasn't known before we did this project – that at the end of the Act there was a piece that was stuck on, which says that: "provided always that after the expiration of the said term of 14 years" – so the Statute awards an exclusive right for the sole right of printing for 14 years – the right "shall return to the authors thereof", if the author is then still living, "for another term of 14 years". So there we have it, a tagged on reversion right. Such discoveries within *Primary Sources* may give you a different story than what you might get from a printed version.

⁵ <https://www.openbookpublishers.com/books/10.11647/obp.0007>

⁶ https://www.copyrighthistory.org/cam/tools/request/showRecord.php?id=record_uk_1710

Figure 1: An Act for the Encouragement of Learning, by Vesting the Copies of Printed Books in the Authors or Purchasers of such Copies, During the Times therein mentioned, 1710, 8 Anne, c.19 (scanned from parchment copy in the UK Parliamentary Archives)

The next document I want to show you is one of my favourites, to which I haven't yet written the commentary. This is a woodcut from 1504 by Albrecht Dürer (1471-1528),⁷ a German Renaissance artist and one of the first commercially minded artists. From a woodcut you could run perhaps about 2,000 copies. For the first time there was a possibility to exploit artistic works in a mass market. Here is his famous AD monogram. Dürer appealed in many ways to a growing bourgeois market. The Biblical scenes are set in contemporary German settings. You see the burghers of Nuremberg and landscapes which are local to that environment.

⁷ https://www.copyrighthistory.org/cam/tools/request/showRecord.php?id=record_i_1504

*Figure 1: 'Joachim and Anne Meeting at the Golden Gate', a woodcut from Albrecht Dürer's cycle *Life of the Virgin* (1504), plagiarized by Marcantonio Raimondi (scanned from prints held in the British Museum).*

This copy on the right side was made in Italy by Marcantonio Raimondi. He may have thought: that's a new way of making money, so we'll make money too. There are small adjustments, the birds have disappeared and the arch looks a little bit more orderly in the Renaissance Italy sense, but Dürer's AD trademark was reproduced with it. We have evidence that there was litigation about this copying in Venice. We don't have the text but a reference to a legal dispute. After that, the monogram disappeared but reprints persisted, without the logo. The archive includes documents of this type that speak to the practice and market reality of its time.

Now moving to the Privilege of 1511:⁸ Dürer obtained a privilege from the Holy Roman Emperor of the German nation, Maximilian. This is the form in which the privilege was communicated to the world with a quite powerful appeal: "Woe to you, ambushers of other people's labour and talent!" and it says things that are not very likely going to happen: "You will find yourself in the greatest danger". The message appears to be: "Don't reprint my stuff, or else!"

⁸ https://www.copyrighthistory.org/cam/tools/request/showRecord.php?id=record_d_1511b

Printed at Nuremberg by the painter Albrecht Dürer in the year Fifteen hundred and twenty-one

Woe to you, ambusher of other people's labour and talent. Beware of laying your rash hand on our work. Know you not what the most glorious Roman Emperor Maximilian has conceded to us? - that no one shall be allowed to re-print these pictures from spurious blocks, nor sell them within the imperial realm. And if you do so, through spite or covetousness, not only will your goods be confiscated, but you will also find yourself in the greatest danger.

Figure 2: Colophon to Albrecht Dürer's woodcut cycle *Life of the Virgin* with reference to an earlier Imperial Privilege (scanned from a copy in the Germanisches Nationalmuseum, Nuremberg)

This is the kind of thing you will find in *Primary Sources on Copyright*, and much more. The national editors have selected documents. These may be contracts, they may be legislative history. Mostly they are traditional legal documents. That's an issue people will probably raise in this discussion: how is copyright history constructed.

I want to conclude my opening remarks with the question: Why copyright history? Why should we care about what happened hundreds of years ago? Why should we try to understand what the invention of the printing press did to cultural production and consumption? Why should we think about the nineteenth century emergence of the author as the centre point of copyright law?

Well, we started this project, as I would see it now, as part of a global wave. There was an interest, a growing interest in copyright history around the year 2000. This may come as no surprise because histories are often invented in a crisis of legitimacy. The digital shock hit the creative industries hard, production and consumption was not going to be as it was before. If there's a crisis of legitimacy, then people turn to history, because history has normative force. As I write

here in my notes: there was no history of colonialism, gender, fashion, or crime until there was a contemporary demand to explain and justify. The crisis of the digital was a crisis of the economy, of industry, but it was also a doctrinal crisis in some ways, because concepts, distinctions between original and copy, between private and public, no longer seemed to work in the way they used to in our field. You can understand the *Primary Sources* project as an attempt to revisit the stories of progress we have told ourselves.

We were also particularly interested in tensions and paradoxes that emerged through this examination. For example, the growth of the authorial consciousness happens at the same time as modes of industrial exploitation. On the one hand, you have the focus on what some people call the romantic author – the genius, a personality context of creation – on which the law is supposed to be formed, on the other hand exploitation becomes more and more industrial exactly at the same time. We are interested in these kind of paradoxical tensions within the journey. Today I think we still struggle to relate norms of communication and norms of transaction. In some ways copyright law creates markets, in another it is a tool of censorship (as we've seen in the history of privileges). Copyright law regulates, encourages *and* limits communication. This is why copyright history matters.

This was my quick run through. Hopefully it gave a flavour for why we should be interested in history, and why these documents may tell us a story that we did not expect, and perhaps explain why we make some of the choices we are making today.

Let me hand over to Lionel Bently who will now ask some searching questions.

Lionel Bently

Thanks, Martin.

We are really delighted to have been able to expand the *PSOC* project from five jurisdictions that the AHRC initially funded to what is now (depending on how you count these) twelve jurisdictions, and to have been able to deepen the contributions of some of the existing sections, particularly France and the UK. The resource – still an editorial project – has grown and grown. Originally intended to be 190 core documents with commentaries, transcriptions and translations, the resource now has 360 or so. And as Martin just told you there are well over 700 documents in the archive as a whole.

The resource now has much more content than before. The commentaries take the reader to a wider range of different political and social contexts, and one can only be stunned by (and grateful for) the erudition of the multiple national editors. All that material is, of course,

important to understanding the sources themselves and how they have been regarded within the literature.

Nevertheless, the expansion of the resource raises important questions and these are questions that we have asked the national editors to think about. First, have we learnt anything that is different from this expansion? Is there anything here that transforms our thinking? Are the stories we have added different in important ways to the stories that were told in the commentaries on the initial five jurisdictions? Do the newly added materials provoke ways of reconceiving the pre-existing entries or new lines of enquiry? Do we need to rethink what was being said about the UK, France, Germany etc, in the light of the records that we now have in relation to Portugal, Spain, The Netherlands, Scandinavia, Jewish history and the Vatican?

For example, in the initial jurisdictions we saw the precursors of copyright in various forms of “privileges” granted primarily to printers (though sometimes to authors); a shift towards modern public laws in the eighteenth and early nineteenth centuries, giving rights initially to authors, but in the form of property that could be ceded to publishers and other exploiters. Can we see in the added jurisdictions matters that qualify, contradict or add complexity to this narrative?

Similarly, in the first stage of the project, one persistent question was how far privilege systems emerged spontaneously in response to specific (e.g. economic, religious) forces developing in parallel in roughly the same time periods, and how far they were developed through processes of copying and imitation (driven for example by processes of competition between national economies)? Was the Venetian practice of the late 15th century the “origin” of most of the 16th century privilege systems, or are the regimes better understood as arising independently and thus being distinct? And having broadened out the countries treated (and included, in particular, non-state based entities such as Jewish law), can we see new patterns, linked, perhaps to political or religious factors? How far did the mix of privileges with censorship and guild regulation vary? Or, if the different privilege systems were developed through processes of imitation and copying, what evidence do we have of this in the new material that has been added? What, if any, were the processes of transmission? And were there adaptations or differences in effect from transplanting the idea of exclusive privileges from one context to another?

Moreover, in its original form, we saw privilege systems that did not (initially at least) distinguish between “cultural” and “technological” contributions; that the system operated in a “reactive” manner, responding to particular circumstances rather than embodying a pre-defined idea of subject matter; and that while many of the privileges were granted to printers of books some went to music publishers, map-makers or engravers. In contrast, in the eighteenth and

nineteenth centuries, distinct conceptualisations of the subject matter of rights emerged – defining a field “copyright”– that extended beyond books and maps to sculptures, paintings and photographs. In the added jurisdictions, do we see alternative trajectories or conceptualisations? What were the factors that drove the “modernisation” of copyright towards adoption of abstract, forward looking categories of subject matter?

After the project’s first stage, one was able to trace a “dialogue” between legal systems, particularly from the mid-eighteenth century: the English literary property debates of the 1760s and 1770s were reflected in German debates over the wrongfulness of reprinting; the discussions of Bulwer Lytton’s proposal for “dramatic property” in the 1830s in Britain referenced, in particular, French laws; the French 1841 debates on term of copyright acknowledged the limited terms in “England, Germany, Spain, Russia, America” as well as Holland. The dialogues are both in terms of the ideas justifying protection of “literary and artistic property” and the positive means of doing so (rights, duration, practical administration). Do the additional jurisdictions have the same characteristics? Are certain influences more pronounced? Do the dialogues mostly work as reasons to expand protection in terms of works, rights or duration?

In the project’s conception, we had in mind that national editors would not limit themselves to formal law, but would try and include materials that reflected practice: for example discussing contracts between authors and publishers or painters, engravers and publishers. The idea was to examine aspects of law in action as well as “law in the books.” How far has this ambition been continued in the added jurisdictions? Is it realistic to think that the resource can offer a meaningful account of “law in action”? Are there any interesting features we can see in the comparative history of contractual practice (e.g. the emergence of royalty-based agreements)? Should we consider further expanding these aspects of the resource?

Those are my questions that I have asked the national editors to reflect on. I have also asked them to think about the way the resource should develop looking forward.

As we move forward, do the national editors have views on what we should do? Should we increase depth in jurisdictions? If so, in what way? Of course, there are some entries that have yet to be fully completed by the original editors, and we will continue to fill those gaps. And we are always keen to involve in the project those doing new research on the existing jurisdictions.

Beyond those, there are certain obvious moves in terms of formal law e.g. expand the Italian coverage to cover other city states, expand the coverage up to 1900 (as with Germany, France, UK and US) or perhaps extend the timeframe for all jurisdictions into the twentieth century (say

1930). Another possibility is to introduce distinct sections on international initiatives: pre-Berne; Berne; (and if we moved into the 20th century) the Inter-American initiatives.

Another possibility is that we should focus elsewhere – for example, try to include more resources that will help us understand the empirical impact of the laws, and their institutional frameworks. Alternatively, or additionally, we could continue to expand the geographical breadth of the coverage. If so, one obvious way would be to include material on the relationship between existing jurisdictions and their colonies as we are doing with Portugal’s relationship with Brazil. For example, we could include sections on the extension, adaptation, etc of British laws to Australia, Canada, India etc. Alternatively, we could seek to include countries or jurisdictions which come from different heritage such as China, Korea, Japan, which have not been thought of as having important links to western/European origins that drove the international phase.

These are my questions to the national editors and we will now hand over to them to see what they have to say.

Martin Kretschmer

We will now ask the national editors to take the stage. Elena Cooper is here, who is the co-chair of the larger conference on 16-17 October 2023 involving the national editors (of which this Public Lecture forms a part) – *Celebrating Fifteen Years of Primary Sources on Copyright 1450-1900*.⁹ We have some of our national editors online too: José Bellido, Joanna Kostyła and Jane Ginsburg.

I said we would give the word alphabetically to each editor, but chair’s privilege goes to the co-chair. Elena, you have the first take.

Elena Cooper, co-editor for Britain/UK.

Thank you to Martin and Lionel. So, that’s more than a few questions for the national editors!

I am going to address the question: when we add new material are we really uncovering new stories, fresh takes, or is it just a repeat of what we already know? Well, this is a really good question for me to answer, because this is part of the story of why I was asked to be a co-editor for the British/UK section.

I joined the project in 2018. The UK was one of the original jurisdictions. By that time, Ronan Deazley had already done a fabulous job of curating 50 key documents for the British Section.

⁹ <https://www.create.ac.uk/blog/2023/10/16/fifteen-years-of-primary-sources-on-copyright-1450-1900-glasgow-16-17-october-2023/>

And that had been launched, as one of the first sections, at the Stationers' Hall conference in 2008. So, the decision, on the part of Martin and Lionel, to appoint me as co-editor some ten years later – in 2018 – was to add a new perspective – to add different stories to Ronan's existing section.

And that new perspective relates to a specific moment in copyright history scholarship – interestingly, that's a moment that united both Katie Scott and I (though we never planned it). In 2018, both Katie and I published the first monographs on the history of copyright relating to the visual arts: Katie's *Becoming Property* (2018, Yale University Press)¹⁰ is about French copyright; and my *Art and Modern Copyright* (2018, CUP)¹¹ about UK copyright. And one of my central findings was that the protection of visual art, in the nineteenth century, added something new to copyright debates. Beyond points of basic principle, introducing copyright for painting, for instance, was not simply about transposing established literary copyright principles to new subject matter. Rather, nineteenth century artistic copyright debates were precisely about articulating what was *distinct* about art and, from that, formulating appropriate legal rules, that often differed from those protecting literature and books.

¹⁰ <https://yalebooks.yale.edu/book/9780300222791/becoming-property/#:~:text=Description,century%20to%20the%20French%20Revolution.>

¹¹ <https://www.create.ac.uk/blog/2021/04/12/new-working-paper-introduction-to-art-and-modern-copyright-the-contested-image/>

Figure 3: Katie Scott (2018) *Becoming Property: Art, Theory, and Law in Early Modern France*, Yale University Press (scan of cover)

Figure 4: Elena Cooper (2018) *Art and Modern Copyright: The Contested Image*, University of Cambridge Press (scan of cover)

So, my specific remit, as co-editor for Britain, was to bring to the archive documents that reflected that difference. And that includes, for example, pro-collector proposals repeatedly presented to Parliament – and endorsed by the Royal Commission on Copyright in 1878 – where copyright was seen not just about protecting artists, but *also* as a means of *restricting* painters from repeating, in the same medium, their own paintings that had been sold, to preserve the uniqueness and therefore the financial value of the original painting – so to preserve the value of the physical property owned by the collector. You can read about that in my commentary to document uk_1869.¹² And while you're doing that, please also take a look at uk_1879b:¹³ the Royal Academy of Arts' Memorial to the Government in 1879. That's a document provided courtesy of the Royal Academy of Arts archive in London, which is the painters' response to those pro-collector proposals. That is a revealing document because the Royal Academy is proposing a *compromise* position: yes, copyright would remain with the painter, but there would be a special provision, preventing painters from producing 'replicas' of their works they had sold. In law, of course, it is always about how you define terms, so, if you take a look at the painters' proposals fleshed out in the 1890s – e.g. in UK_1899¹⁴ – you will see that the Royal Academy proposes that

¹² https://www.copyrighthistory.org/cam/tools/request/showRecord.php?id=record_uk_1869

¹³ https://www.copyrighthistory.org/cam/tools/request/showRecord.php?id=record_uk_1879b

¹⁴ https://www.copyrighthistory.org/cam/tools/request/showRecord.php?id=record_uk_1899

'replicas' should be defined narrowly, only to cover works 'so nearly the same size' and works that 'rendered doubtful the identity of the original work.' These documents are a good example of how, when you add new material, you may reveal quite different perspectives: the different constellation of interests in the art object, for instance, as compared with books, resulted in the debate of quite distinct legal ideas.

Patricia Akester, co-editor for Portugal and Brazil.

The first thing is to say how wonderful it has been to be part of such a marvellous project. I'll make two points only and they are not major points. The first one is that we edited *PSOC* Portugal in a conservative manner, and we are considering doing *PSOC* Brazil (once we get there, it'll take while) in a different way: we might look more at the law in action (which is one of the suggestions that Lionel Bently put forward), that is, court cases, contracts and that sort of thing. *PSOC* Brazil may be subject to a different approach from the one we have had regarding *PSOC* Portugal. The second point is the time frame. In this connection it might be interesting to extend the time frame until the 1930s or to include references to the twentieth century within existing entries, as there are some interesting legislative documents in Portugal in the early twentieth century. I mentioned one at the academic conference this morning, which is a decree that was enacted in 1926, instituted perpetuity of intellectual property and was in force for 40 years – not something one can ignore. That's my very modest contribution.

José Bellido, editor for Spain.

Thank you, Martin, Lionel, Elena, and CREATE for organising the conference. I am editor of the Spanish section and it's a great privilege to be here to celebrate 15 years of *Primary Sources on Copyright*. The Spanish section was completed a decade ago, so it is a bit younger than the original countries or jurisdictions and it has documents from different archives in Madrid, Barcelona, Seville, Salamanca, and other Spanish cities, and municipalities. As it was not part of the original funding bid, the Spanish section was funded by other institutions. I have to acknowledge: *ALADDA*, that is the Spanish section of *ALAI*, and the University Oberta de Catalunya. Also, I had the collaboration of two other academics: one was Raquel Xalabarder, and the other one is Ramón Cases Vallès, who sadly passed away recently.

The Spanish section has, as you can see, 50 documents and around 20 commentaries, and as a national editor I have reflected on the sources recently in a book chapter that is called 'IP and The Question of the Archive' (in *Handbook of Intellectual Property Research: Lenses, Methods and*

Perspectives, ed. Calboli and Montagnani, 2021, OUP).¹⁵ One of the concerns that I had, was how to reflect something that Lionel Bently had suggested: how to make what is a jurisdictional section reflect also on transnational moves, or how perhaps the comparative structure given to the editors could evolve into a sort of meta-history or teleological history of copyright law. Perhaps that's not a problem at all. Although there are limits, there are also possibilities and hints for future research or things that surprise you when you look back 10 or 15 years later. And there were two things that caught my attention when I revisited the Spanish section recently: two documents. One is a 1506 printing privilege (s_1506),¹⁶ and the other one is the 1898 Treaty of Peace between the US and Spain (s_1898).¹⁷

Figure 5: *Antonij nebriffensis gramatici iuris civilis lexicon*, Printing privilege of Antonio de Nebrij (1506)(Biblioteca Histórica de la Universidad Complutense)

The first document, the privilege, is a dispute and shows how there might be a possibility of exploring a pre-history of copyright law in Spain by looking at the authorial invisibility and the constraints experienced by Jewish authors that were converted into Catholicism. I thought that

¹⁵ <https://global.oup.com/academic/product/handbook-of-intellectual-property-research-9780198826743?cc=us&lang=en&>

¹⁶ https://www.copyrighthistory.org/cam/tools/request/showRecord.php?id=record_s_1506

¹⁷ https://www.copyrighthistory.org/cam/tools/request/showRecord.php?id=record_s_1898

was quite interesting. There is a similar reference to Sephardic culture, music, community in Spain somewhere in the section; I think that is hinted in the Spanish section.

Figure 6: Treaty of Peace between the United States and Spain (1898)(Archivo del Ministerio de Asuntos Exteriores, AMAE, siglo XIX, Tratados, 0519)

The second document is the Treaty of Peace between the US and Spain that connects the copyright history of those countries to a colonial history or post-colonial history of Cuba, Puerto Rico, and the Philippine Islands.

What do these two documents have in common? What they have in common is that they show the potential of *Primary Sources on Copyright*: they can be conceptualized as a type of pre-writing – a note for a history to come. The interest in the Spanish section, in my view, is not only in what it tells us about a Spanish copyright history as a spirit of national identity, but precisely how the Other was constituted or expelled in that history. And that’s a potential of the archive to

understand what happened in those histories and what role copyright or the privilege system played in those histories.

I also have a couple of points about the future development of the Spanish section. One of the limitations of the section is that I have been living for 20 years in the UK. I don't have the possibility to spend as much time in Spain. But if I come back to Spain, I hope to be able to add more sources and commentaries. One thing that Marius Buning, the next speaker, will be talking about, and I have a lot of expectations about, is what his project *Before Copyright*¹⁸ could bring into the existing sections, such as the Spanish privilege system etc. I will hand over to Marius on that note. I'm really looking forward what his project can contribute to other sections of *Primary Sources on Copyright*. Thank you.

Marius Buning, co-editor for the Netherlands and editor for Scandinavia.

Thank you very much, José, for that generous introduction. My name is Marius Buning and I am a professor at the University of Oslo. Being of Dutch origin, I first got involved with *Primary Sources on Copyright* as part of the Dutch section, working with Stef van Gompel. But I am here now as the editor of the Scandinavian section, which was launched today. *Primary Sources on Copyright* now includes 32 documents on the Scandinavian history of copyright. I will perhaps say something about these documents later. But first I want to reflect briefly on the questions that Lionel Bently circulated to us in advance.

Reading through Lionel's questions, I noticed that a number of them were about what "we" have learned from adding new jurisdictions, which made me wonder who "we" actually is. To turn things around, I wanted to start by saying how much "we" (as one of those newly added jurisdictions) have also learned from the existing sections of *Primary Sources on Copyright*. I think that, particularly for the Scandinavian section, it has been enormously important to work in the context of *Primary Sources on Copyright*, for example to see international connections. Legal history in Scandinavia is often still written from a 'local' perspective: the Norwegians, the Swedes, the Danes each tell their own story, and they don't always communicate much with each other, or internationally. Working together as a team on *Primary Sources on Copyright* has allowed us to do things a bit differently.

For example, at the academic conference celebrating *Primary Sources on Copyright* this morning, we spoke about a document from the Scandinavian section from 1841, about the limitation of the term of copyright protection in Sweden. And now we know that this document

¹⁸ <https://www.hf.uio.no/iakh/english/research/projects/before-copyright/>

should actually be seen in the context of French debates – which is something we would have known little about before being involved in *Primary Sources on Copyright*. So that's very interesting.

I sit here as a bit of an outsider, since I write mainly about Dutch history. But one of the things that strikes me about Scandinavia is that things were very different there when compared to other jurisdictions: there were few printing presses, no printing guilds, no Stationers' Company, for example, and no registers. Researching the history of copyright in Scandinavia is therefore also different from researching copyright history in other areas. Nevertheless, in many ways the underlying legal system was similar. There were printing privileges, for example, which I think has something to do with the common heritage of Roman and church law. And this is also part of the *Before Copyright* project that I am setting up at the University of Oslo, which is trying to find out more about these connections between different jurisdictions and legal systems in the period 1400 to 1800 (which is a slightly different time frame to *Primary Sources on Copyright*).

Primary Sources on Copyright is a great project. The focus is very clear, and I think it is a great tool for students to familiarise themselves with the subject. It also creates a community of people; otherwise, we wouldn't be up here as a group talking to each other from different disciplines. So that's great too. I would suggest that we keep the focus (if I can give some advice in response to the pre-circulated questions). I am a little hesitant about whether such projects can give a full account of living law over a period of 400 years, for example. I think the original plan wasn't too bad! Maybe we should just build on what we have and expand where we can. So colonial histories should definitely be included. But if we were to include Chinese history, for example, I think we would have to talk about the Song Empire and that might take the focus away. But that is something we could discuss at a later stage.

Victor Drummond, editor for Brazil.

Thank you. Well, I am Victor, and I have a Scottish surname: Drummond. But, that's perhaps not very interesting, as many people have Scottish names here, but I am happy to point that out! I have some really brief points. When we write commentaries we need to reflect not only on the documents, but some part of the history of that moment, and local history, and some things that can bring a kind of colour, because sometimes it is difficult just to study law. Copyright is a very interesting area to study because when we study or research copyright we in fact research art, culture, literature, music. I think it is very important to take a look at copyright as part of a complex of knowledge and possibilities. The national documents reflect this to some extent. This is my first time meeting my colleagues from *Primary Sources on Copyright*, and I am very

excited to continue the project. Patricia Akester and I have been talking about our section covering Portugal and Brazil. It's peculiar, because in Brazil we have just a century of documents. In Brazil, we had some previous legislation that initially dealt with the topic of copyright, such as the decree that created the royal printing in Brazil in 1808. Anyway, the first copyright statute in the country was published in 1898 (Law 496). It's a very short history and complementary to talk about Portugal and Brazil together.

Jane Ginsburg, editor for the Vatican.

In response to the question of what does adding jurisdictions add to the resource, in the case of the Vatican documents, I believe they provide a very different perspective on early printing privileges from the one that emerges from some of the other national sections, notably concerning the regime's beneficiaries and its orientation. I discussed the regime of Papal privileges at the academic conference this morning, so I won't dwell on that any further. For a specific example of how additional jurisdictions contribute, I think if you compare the Italian section, at least as originally written, and the Vatican section, you'll get a very different impression of how the printing privilege system worked, which might nuance the account in the Italian national section. That observation in turn brings me to another of Lionel's questions: the cross-jurisdictional interest of including multiple jurisdictions in the archive. I think that having more jurisdictions enriches the project by making it possible to compare how different jurisdictions address similar questions: whether they influenced each other, whether they had national peculiarities. Having all that information and analysis in one place enhances the overall utility and interest of the Primary Sources project. By contrast, I think I'm less convinced, at least so far, of whether we should open an international section. The Berne Convention and its precursors are now well documented online, thanks to WIPO, and there is no shortage of commentaries on those documents. As a result, international copyright is an area where *Primary Sources on Copyright* may not add to what's already available elsewhere, although it might not be a bad thing to link to those sources.

Stef van Gompel, co-editor for the Netherlands.

My name is Stef van Gompel. Together with Marius Buning, I am the national editor of the Section for The Netherlands. Already on this point – my collaboration with Marius – I want to make an important observation: that it is very valuable to work and to approach copyright history from an interdisciplinary perspective. After I started the Dutch section and Marius joined, the Dutch section has only improved. As a lawyer – I am Professor of Intellectual Property Law in Amsterdam – I am nuanced in the laws that I study, but sometimes less nuanced in the historical

perspective that I take. Marius, who is an historian, helps to refine the historical consistencies in my research and I, on my part, help him to straighten the legal elements in his research. I think that combination works really well. Those who work in interdisciplinary discourse immediately understand the value of working together with someone from another discipline. And that kind of co-operation is what *Primary Sources on Copyright* truly stimulates.

A second point is indeed the value of adding new sections to *Primary Sources on Copyright*. We, as national editors, are all specialised in our own national jurisdictions and learning from the other jurisdictions is essential to enrich our research. I am currently working on a research paper on the exclusion of school books from copyright protection in the Netherlands. Since 1625, school books were excluded from the privilege system in Holland, and later on, until 1881, they were also denied copyright protection in The Netherlands. This exclusion is remarkable and sheds an interesting perspective on the current discourse about open access and open educational resources. So already there, you see that that we can learn a lot from history. But studying this from the Dutch perspective also makes us wonder: How is this different elsewhere? Do similar exclusions exist in Germany, France, England or other countries? And where do I find evidence of this? I am very lucky that today the Scandinavian section was launched, as we found out that there is actually a similar exclusion in a Danish statute from 1741. So the exclusion is not entirely exclusive to the Netherlands, which directly adds new perspectives to my research. So, I would really welcome expanding jurisdictions, at least if they have such new insights to add.

Martin Kretschmer

Friedemann Kawohl is next, who is a musicologist.

Friedmann Kawohl, editor for German speaking countries.

Thank you for all the questions, Lionel, from which I will focus on just one.

One point on exclusions: in Germany there was an exclusion from performance rights in broadcasting for prisons, until the 1960s.

I am the editor for the German-speaking countries, as we called all these different jurisdictions, which included more than 300 countries of the Holy Roman Empire, and later also Polish part of Prussia and the Kingdom of Sardinia, which belonged to Austria. So, there were quite different jurisdictions in this part.

Who actually uses *Primary Sources on Copyright*? And who do we want to use it? Scholars working in legal history, in book history, art history, media archaeology, and social history of

printers and authors, or in the history of censorship regimes, certainly have another focus than legal scholars who might use ideas from the past to work out possible future copyright regulations. And 15 years ago for us it was without doubt that printing privileges of the sixteenth to eighteenth century are an essential part of a history of copyright. Today, I am not anymore convinced.

What is it that we can learn from those privileges? We can see that they regulate the market of books, printed music, and printed art. We can see that some printers, publishers, or sometimes authors, could economically benefit from their personal relations to the rulers or to their deputies. And we can see that rulers did grant privileges to control the knowledge and the ideas dispersed in their lands rather than to set incentives for an open book market, let alone for the protection of any author's personal or scholarly integrity. Thus, printing privileges probably do not provide much that could help us finding a way for future regulation systems. However, if the project for the next 15 years is to address also the interests of book historians and historians, the privilege section should be expanded. There has since been a lot of research, and the documents that these subsequent research papers deal with could easily be implemented, together with commentaries and translations that would give an overview on the current state of research.

And the other point raised by Lionel Bently: of expansion of *Primary Sources on Copyright*. When we were working on this project, Martin Kretschmer has mentioned, there were imminent changes in the marketing of copyright. The future of national organised copyright collecting societies were in question, and people in the music industry did not foresee the rapid growth of streaming services at that time. Our interest in the history of copyright was triggered, at least to some extent, by the chance to find ideas for possible future regulation. I found in a recent CREATE Working Paper, the paper by Elena Cooper ('AI and Performers' Rights in Historical Perspective', *CREATE Working Paper 2023/09*),¹⁹ who argues that we should now debate the scope of protection for performers since it is possible, meanwhile, to let AI systems calculate voices and images of actors, and thus making some human actors, singers, or voiceover artists redundant. To reflect on the contemporary problem, Elena draws a line to the mid nineteenth century situation, where new technologies of photography and printing demanded new levels of protection for visual artists and printsellers, who claimed in court that otherwise pictures would not be painted. Elena then refers to a common law case, where film actors in 1910 successfully claimed that contract clauses, preventing actors from using their stage-name pseudonym once they left a film company's employment, were unenforceable. When the range of documents

¹⁹ <https://www.create.ac.uk/blog/2023/09/15/new-create-working-paper-ai-and-performers-rights-in-historical-perspective-by-elena-cooper/>

would be opened beyond copyright in a narrow sense, to legislation and cases, tackling personality, rights of authors and the relation between authors and their works the *Primary Sources on Copyright* project may help copyright scholars in the next 15 years to meet the challenges of AI.

Joanna Kostyło, editor for Italy.

First and foremost, I would like to express my gratitude to the organizers, and especially to Martin Kretschmer, for extending the invitation to this conference. I would like to share some general thoughts on the questions raised by Lionel Bently.

In consideration of Lionel's concern that the *PSOC* approach may exhibit a certain bias towards a history of the book, I am mindful of the challenges encountered in my capacity as the editor of the Italian section. This section comprises some of the earliest documents dating back to the fifteenth and sixteenth centuries, and a distinct challenge has arisen in the effort to contextualize these materials with meaningful insights within the framework of legal discourse, particularly given their evident bias towards the history of printing. Nevertheless, issues related to the physical and cultural dimensions of books as objects of copyright, including the presentation of authors within para-textual elements that frequently envelop the primary content of a literary work under protection, or the materiality of the early printing privileges themselves, may enable a more comprehensive analysis of the historical significance of specific documents and cases.

It has been truly heartening to witness the growth of the database. Certainly, with the inclusion of new jurisdictions and sources, there is a risk of repeating stories that had already been told. So, as Lionel asks, do we need more documents at all? The answer depends on whether we want to limit our narrative to a strictly legal discourse or adopt a holistic approach and navigate the history of copyright within a broader cultural framework. Do we wish to delve into cultural attitudes towards creativity, authorship, and intellectual property? Furthermore, shall we explore public discourse, academic debates, artistic movements, and the perspectives of key cultural figures to gain a comprehensive understanding of diverse viewpoints on intellectual property? Do we aim to understand how various cultures and societies, including marginalized communities, developed unique approaches to intellectual property, and how these attitudes shape legal frameworks? In my view, the inclusion of specific types of new documents to the database, rather than necessarily the complete set of sources pertaining to a new jurisdiction, has the potential to cultivate such a holistic and nuanced understanding of the history of copyright by integrating legal developments into a broader cultural perspective. Neil Netanel's

contribution to *PSOC* on Jewish copyright is particularly relevant in this context, underscoring the role of cultural and religious factors in shaping legal frameworks and practices.

Lionel's question about expanding *Primary Sources* to countries like China is directly linked to this matter. Historically, China and the Far East have been shaped by the influences of Confucianism and Taoism, each bearing distinctive and disparate sensitivities compared to European or Western cultures. Therefore, it might be worthwhile to inquire whether they harbour a copyright history that is distinct and worthy of exploration, or at the very least, comparison with Western historical perspectives. Similarly, a country like Russia presents uncharted terrain for investigation.

Another question pertains to the transnational dimension of the documents and case studies. While the inclusion of Imperial and Papal privileges in the database has partially addressed this concern, it remains one of the most challenging aspects of the entire project. A more concentrated emphasis on cross-border exchanges and the examination of practices related to internationalization and harmonization of specific copyright aspects across jurisdictions could certainly contribute to addressing these lacunae. And here, I would like to highlight the case studied by Jane Ginsburg: a controversy sparked by the Papal privilege concerning the Roman Gregorian calendar. This particular controversy gave rise to diverse responses and legal disputes across Europe, involving Habsburg courts, Poland, and Lithuania. It would be intriguing to explore these events and disputes across jurisdictions.

The final issue I wish to address is the investigation of documents related to complex forms of authorship, such as collaborative authorship, transmission and use of academic lectures, or orphan works with unidentified right holders. To provide an example from my respective area of studies, as early as the sixteenth century, academic lecturers launched legal challenges against unruly students who published their lectures without permission. Another controversial practice from the early modern era involves deceptive forms of authorship, including anonymity and pseudonymity. The latter extends to the creation of multiple counterfeit fictional profiles through various printed works, promoting a distinct agenda on behalf of the author, a practice recognized today as astroturfing. These controversial practices prompted specific responses demanding disclosure and accountability of authors giving rise to significant questions that resonate with contemporary concerns surrounding publications through digital media. Would such cases, along with their accompanying legal challenges linked to attribution, hold relevance for the history of copyright as well as intricate copyright issues that fuel contemporary debates?

To sum up and return to the main question about the future strategies for *PSOC*, from my personal perspective as a cultural historian, a continued commitment to diversity in document types and an expanded geographic reach, without necessarily adding complete set of sources pertaining to new jurisdictions, while cultivating a holistic, multi-cultural, and transnational perspectives, would undoubtedly benefit the project.

Frédéric Rideau, editor for France.

My name is Frédéric Rideau and I am the editor of the French section, with now Katie Scott for visual arts. Most of the sources and the commentaries have been online since 2008, but I have since added 6 commentaries and I would like to thank Elena Cooper because she's watching over my syntax in English. The selection of the sources: like in the other jurisdictions, that often means privileges and decrees. To come back to Joanna Kostyło's question: that is a problem, because, of course, these privileges were granted principally to printers and booksellers. They were forming guilds in France, and the main guild was the Parisian guild. Of course, these medieval structures had a view on how authors could and should claim their potential rights. Of course, if we could add, for example, contracts, that would be a great thing. But the problem is that it is very difficult to find contracts for this period before the French Revolution, and probably after. It would require a huge amount of time to find these sources. But the law in action is really missing. It would be very useful to investigate this in the future, if we can find some contracts, and to have other sources, to expand, in a way, what we can learn from these authors' claims, and especially in the eighteenth century and after.

Katie Scott, co-editor for France.

I am not going to say very much so, because I want to hear from you and the questions that you might have to ask us. I'm a bit of an interloper because I am an art historian and not a legal historian. Frédéric has done a fantastic job for the French section, and I have added four documents which relate to the visual arts. I would say, to encourage you to have a look at them, that one of the things that is interesting about the visual arts in relation to copyright is that the distinction between an intangible and a tangible property in visual art is only beginning to take shape in the early modern period. Whereas with literature there is quite a clear distinction between the intangible text and the tangible printing, in the case of printed images, that distinction is not so clear. And so, the discussion about the materiality of the image is still very much a live issue until well into the nineteenth century.

Elena Cooper

Thank you national editors! Martin and Lionel asked a lot of questions, and we've had a number of answers to those questions. But what about the question of who uses *Primary Sources*? Martin and I also wanted to ask the national editors if they had particular anecdotes of uses – perhaps surprising ones – of *Primary Sources*? Perhaps we have some users in the audience?

Certainly, in my view, I think one of the great strengths of the archive – and why I was so excited to be involved – is the way in which it opens up the primary sources of legal history, not just to you – the public – but also to scholars of different disciplines. My example of someone from another discipline using this archive is from art history. In 2020, the art historian Julie Codell, published an important scholarly contribution to art history: *Victorian Artists' Autograph Replicas* (2020, Routledge)²⁰ which places centre-stage Victorian artists' practices of repeating their own work. That was published in 2020, and as I've said, the expansion of copyright history to cover visual art happened in 2018, and it was lovely to see – in both the editorial introduction and particular essays in that anthology – art historical arguments that are, in some way, shaped by copyright history scholarship. Specifically, at least in one of the essays in that art history anthology, there is a direct reference to this archive and to use of its primary source material. It is through an archive of this nature, that an art historian can access and reflect on primary sources on legal history.

Are there any other examples of uses of *Primary Sources* that the national editors would like to discuss?

Martin Kretschmer

Of the 300,000!

Marius Buning

Just one word, since it was mentioned, in relation to my *Before Copyright* project on printing privileges. For me, Jane Ginsburg's work in *Primary Sources on Copyright*, and also her absolutely excellent article on papal privileges (Ginsburg, Jane C. 'Proto-Property in Literary and Artistic Works: Sixteenth-Century Papal Printing Privileges', *Columbia Journal of Law & the Arts* (2013, 36, no. 3, 345–458),²¹ really shows that adding different jurisdictions is important because you get a different picture. The *Primary Sources* website allows you to see things side by side, and

²⁰ <https://www.routledge.com/Victorian-Artists-Autograph-Replicas-Auras-Aesthetics-Patronage-and/Codell/p/book/9780367145828>

²¹ https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2650152

that is really excellent. Also in that sense, *Primary Sources* was really essential in putting together the *Before Copyright* project.

Elena Cooper

So, let's now open to the floor for questions from all of you.

Kris Erickson

I am Kris Erickson and I am a new appointment at CREATE, as Professor of Social Data Science. Your resource is super impressive, congratulations. It is growing clearly in size, and you could perhaps describe it as a corpus. My question is whether or not you've considered (or maybe you are already) working across data science or digital humanities. Perhaps to try to uncover new insights or link the data with other existing data sets to uncover new insights that might be of mutual interest even more radically and cross-disciplinary?

Martin Kretschmer

I have two observations. CREATE also hosts Stationers' Register Online²² (discussed in our webinar on Papal Privileges and the Stationers' Register),²³ which we thought about linking into PSOC. But these things are tough. As Marius pointed out earlier today, the English documents in Primary Sources at the moment are not machine readable, because we have not transcribed English language sources. This doesn't help, but you are right: this is a corpus. Second point. It is also a corpus with a particular editorial design which makes me slightly worried about drawing quantitative results from it. Maybe if you could quantify our biases!

Any other reactions to that?

Marius Buning

It would be very possible to use *Primary Sources* as the basis for a relational database. It would be great if someone in the audience felt called to actually do that as a project, for a Master's or PhD, for example. I was thinking of taking some of the documents out and putting them into my own relational database – I think it would certainly be possible to expand on that in the future.

²² <https://stationersregister.online/>

²³ <https://www.create.ac.uk/blog/2022/07/14/new-create-copyright-history-resources-two-working-papers-and-further-vatican-sources-by-jane-ginsburg-for-primary-sources-on-copyright-1450-1900/>

Martin Kretschmer

I think it is sensible to close at this point. We should also acknowledge Oren Bracha, US national editor, who isn't here today, and also Neil Netanel who was mentioned earlier. It has been a fantastic day already, and more tomorrow. Something will happen I am sure.

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